

The Sifting Silence—Jesus’s Pause

John 6:65

Part of a longer analysis into the pauses in speech in the Bible

See *A Study in Silence*

ABSTRACT

This essay examines Jesus’s pause in John 6:65 as a deliberate moment of spiritual sifting. Following hard sayings that unsettled many disciples, the silence exposed motives and prompted self-examination. Some withdrew, unable to move beyond a literal or material outlook, while others remained, held by a deeper loyalty despite incomplete understanding. The pause was perhaps an emotional moment for Jesus. It was not coercive but allowed space for a response. In this tense silence, allegiance was revealed and motives were tested.

John 6:65

καὶ ἔλεγεν διὰ τοῦτο εἶρηκα ὑμῖν ὅτι οὐδεὶς δύναται ἐλθεῖν πρὸς με ἐὰν μὴ ἦ δεδομένον αὐτῷ ἐκ τοῦ πατρὸς

Jesus said, “He that feeds on my flesh and drinks my blood has everlasting life, and I shall resurrect him at the last day; for my flesh is true food, and my blood is true drink” (John 6:54, 55)*. Many took his words literally, saying, “This speech is shocking; who can listen to it?” (verse 60). The metaphor that Jesus used was no doubt meant to provoke—he wanted disciples who would not be scandalised by a misunderstanding. In verse 47 he had said, “He that believes has everlasting life”. Jesus equated believing with eating his flesh and drinking his blood. So believing has to be more than an acceptance that something exists or is true (James 2:19; Hebrews 11:6).

By way of an aside, the metaphor of eating and drinking suggests a variety of meaning: both are vital for life, both satisfy a need, both revitalise and empower, both can promote good health, both are a pleasure and are social, both processes absorb and integrate the food and drink making it part of us.

Jesus’s flesh and his blood would play an essential role in providing the ransom

* Bible quotations are from the *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, 1984, unless otherwise indicated.

(Matthew 20:28; Ephesians 1:7). His audience had been attracted by the free food on the previous day. But their relationship with Jesus had to go much deeper, in effect ‘eating and drinking’ Jesus, otherwise their relationship with Jesus would not be sustained in the difficult times ahead. Jesus knew that that close relationship would be immeasurably strengthened by an appreciation for the ransom sacrifice. This was and is a serious matter: “For God loved the world so much that he gave his only-begotten Son in order that everyone exercising faith in him might not be destroyed but have everlasting life” (John 3:16).

We understand the importance of Jesus’s sacrificial death now, but at that time it was quite some request. Not even Jesus’s closest disciples understood the sacrificial route he was having to take. We could of course say that they should have done (Luke 24:25). A year later as they came to Jerusalem “they were imagining that the kingdom of God was going to display itself instantly” (Luke 19:11). And even after his death they asked Jesus, “Lord, are you restoring the kingdom to Israel at this time?” (Acts 1:6).

In response to his disciples’ shock, Jesus said, “Does this stumble you? What, therefore, if you should behold the Son of man ascending to where he was before?” (verses 61, 62). In other words, if you are offended by my metaphor, what if you later discover my true status and my authority for making these comments? How will you feel then? He was appealing to his disciples not to miss the point, not to miss this opportunity to draw closer to God. When they would later realise just who he was, he did not want them to have regrets. No doubt he wanted them to respond like Peter and be loyal even if they did not fully understand (verse 68). Jesus then said: “It is the spirit that is life-giving; the flesh is of no use at all. The sayings that I have spoken to you* are spirit and are life” (verse 63). In its context Jesus must be continuing his appeal for his disciples to understand his eating and drinking metaphor. By understanding it spiritually, his disciples would not be offended, but would benefit by gaining everlasting life (verse 47). There is a possibility that Jesus was making a reference to the free food that he had miraculously provided the day before—the flesh of the fish and the bread. This food had generated tremendous excitement, but had Jesus told them: “Work, not for the

* The Introduction to the *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, 1984 says, “Where ‘you’ is printed in small capital letters, it shows that the pronoun is plural. Also, where the plural number of a verb is not apparent, its plurality is indicated by printing it in small capital letters. If the context already clearly indicates plurality, then no special capitalization is used.”

food that perishes (“the flesh is of no use at all”), but for the food that remains for life everlasting” (verse 27).

“It is not as if the flesh is of no significance: after all, the Word became flesh (1:14). But when all the focus of attention is on the flesh, then the real significance of Jesus is missed, and the kinds of objections raised both by ‘the Jews’ and by ostensible disciples quickly surface” (Carson).

Despite Jesus’s appeals, “even among those who are reckoned to be μαθηταὶ there are unbelievers” (Barrett). So Jesus said: “There are some of YOU that do not believe” (verse 64).

Then Jesus paused.

Jesus had just uncovered something—not all his disciples were trusting him. That was solemn. A subsequent pause would have allowed these disciples a moment to think about his disclosure. Jesus allowed his statement to linger unsoftened, unmitigated. A silence would force self-examination: Is he talking about me? A moment to reflect seriously on which side of the divide they were at that moment. Would they stay with him or leave him?

Throughout the conversation Jesus had been deliberately sifting his followers to allow his Father Jehovah* to examine each one’s motive (Proverbs 17:11). He wanted to make sure that his disciples were not motivated by material benefit, excitement, social pressure, but rather genuine love for his Father. He was going to need a resilient congregation that was loyal to him, a congregation that could go on to help others to become spiritually resilient as they too would face a hostile world (John 15:18, 19).

The pause functions as a test of loyalty. In a moment of tension and uncertainty, loyalties surface. Some had begun to withdraw internally before physically leaving. Others—like Peter—would remain, not because everything was clear, but because their attachment to Jesus was stronger than their confusion. The pause exposed whether their bond was limited or unlimited.

John took advantage of the pause to expand on Jesus’s words: “For from [the] beginning Jesus knew who were the ones not believing and who was the one that would betray him”. When Judas began to lose his loyalty, Jesus, who could read hearts and thoughts, detected this change (Matthew 9:4, *notsty*). As a result the

* See Appendix, page 5.

pause could also be interpreted as an emotional moment for Jesus: the sadness of loss, of other's negative and destructive decisions.

After the pause, Jesus said, "This is why I have said to you, No one can come to me unless it is granted him by the Father" (verse 65). He was referencing what he had said in verse 44: "No man can come to me unless the Father, who sent me, draws him".

The pause marks a transition from observation ("There are some of you that do not believe") to explanation ("No one can come to me unless it is granted him by the Father"), from 'some do not believe' to 'believing depends on the Father's admittance'. They must first confront their own response—Do I believe, or not? Jesus's words confirmed that not all present were being drawn.

"No one can come to me unless it is granted him by the Father" does not mean that the Father will prevent someone who wants his friendship, but Jesus's intent had been to search through the motives of his listeners. The Father would only grant closeness to Jesus to those whose motives were unmixed. The Father does not arbitrarily restrict access, but neither does he grant closeness to those who approach with wrong intentions. Only those who are spiritually hungry and humble are 'granted' closeness (Micah 6:8; Matthew 5:3, 8; Luke 6:21; James 4:10). They are not merely attracted by miracles or material benefit, but are willing to look beyond the fleshly aspects and understand—or at least *want* to understand—the spiritual reality behind Jesus's words. So the sifting accomplished its purpose: it revealed who was truly being drawn by the Father and who was not.

Finally, the pause reflects Jesus's considerate restraint. He could have immediately identified individuals or pressed the point more forcefully. Instead, he gave space for them all to think, to feel the weight of what he had said, and then to choose. We could see the pause an act of patience, allowing the Father's drawing to operate without coercion. It is a dreadful moment when one holds out the opportunity of life and it is met with a refusal to accept it. When the moment is so full of importance and urgency in God's eyes, but it is considered of no importance to one's audience.

66 Owing to this many of his disciples went off to the things behind and would no longer walk with him. 67 Therefore Jesus said to the twelve: "you do not want to go also, do you?" 68 Simon Peter answered him: "Lord, whom shall we go away to? You have sayings of everlasting life; 69 and we have believed and come to know that you are the Holy One of God."

APPENDIX

In the Bible the divine name יהוה occurs almost seven thousand times, more often than any of God's titles, and more often than any other separate Hebrew word.

There are many theophoric names in the Bible. The majority of Bible translators transliterate those names which have the first two syllables of the divine name as Jeho. Hence: Jehonathan, Jehoshua, Jehoshaphat, Jehoahaz, Jehonadab, Jehoram etc. When the Israelites shortened a name they would not abbreviate but they contracted it by removing syllables from the middle of the name. So Jehonathan was reduced to Jonathan; Jehoshua became Joshua; Jehonadab became Jonadab. God's name was contracted to Jah, hence: Elijah, Abijah and Hallelujah etc. Therefore, the divine name must have had three syllables, not two.

We believe that a י is more likely to be transliterated as a y in English, and a ו is more likely to be transliterated as a w. So the divine name could be *Yehowah*. However, most Bible scholars avoid any transliteration. They use the tetragrammaton in Hebrew letters יהוה, or they display the divine name as YHWH. This is all well and good, but it is inconsistent with their transliteration of other Bible names. If they are to be consistent then they should either use Yehonathan for Jonathan or show the Hebrew letters יהנתן, or YWNTN. Sometimes they use *Yahweh* which disregards how names were shortened, and it only has two syllables.

The argument that the vowels of יהוה are those of אֱלֹהֵי does not hold up because the vowels are not the same.

Gesenius pointed out that "Those who consider that יהוה was the actual pronunciation [of God's name] are not altogether without ground on which to defend their opinion. In this way can the abbreviated syllables יהו and יו, with which many proper names begin, be more satisfactorily explained."

We believe that *Jehovah* is a reasonable transliteration of the tetragrammaton.